

The Effect of Compositing on the Isothermal and Cyclic Oxidation Behavior of Titanium Aluminides

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ABSTRACT

The isothermal and cyclic oxidation behavior of TiAl matrix composites containing alumina based fibers were studied over the temperature range of 950 °C to 1070 °C. The isothermal oxidation resistance of TiAl containing 40 wt.% aluminum was unchanged by the addition of pure Al₂O₃ fibers; however, composites reinforced with PRD166 fibers (Al₂O₃-15wt.%ZrO₂) exhibited increased specific weight gains, as compared to monolithic TiAl. The oxide adherence on TiAl, as measured by resistance to spalling during cyclic oxidation, was improved by the addition of both alumina and alumina-zirconia reinforcements. A mechanism for the improved oxide adherence is discussed.

Keywords: Titanium aluminide composites, PRD166, internal oxidation, oxide adherence

1. INTRODUCTION

Titanium aluminides of various compositions are being considered for high temperature structural applications. The combination of high temperature strength, high specific modulus, and improved oxidation resistance over titanium makes titanium aluminides potential replacements for titanium alloys and nickel base superalloys¹. Widespread usage of titanium aluminides, as well as other intermetallic compounds, is currently limited by a lack of room temperature ductility and a susceptibility to environmental degradation by oxidation and hydrogen embrittlement.

Intermetallic compounds containing ductile or brittle reinforcements are being studied as a potential remedy for the inherent limitations of the matrices^{2,3}. However, few researchers have studied the effect of reinforcements on the environmental stability of intermetallic matrix composites. The goal of this study was to evaluate the effect of an oxidation resistant fiber on the isothermal and cyclic oxidation behavior of TiAl composites. It will be shown that even inert fibers, such as alumina, can affect the formation and adherence of a protective oxide scale on titanium aluminides.

2. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

The monolithic and titanium aluminide composites used in this study were produced by powder processing of elemental powders. Two different alumina fibers, FPTM and PRD166TM, were chosen as reinforcements because of their chemical compatibility and low coefficient of thermal expansion mismatch with gamma TiAl, in addition to their stability in oxidizing environments. Both fibers are 20 μm in diameter and were chopped to lengths of approximately 1mm. Fiber FP is 99+% alumina while PRD166 contains 15 wt.% partially stabilized zirconia. The addition of zirconia produces a 50% improvement in room temperature strength and increased strength retention at elevated temperatures, as compared to a pure alumina FP fiber⁴.

The nominal composition of the monolithic TiAl and the matrix of the composites was 40 wt.% (54 at.%) aluminum, which corresponds to single phase gamma on the Ti-Al phase diagram. The chopped fibers were mixed with elemental titanium and aluminum powders, cold isostatically pressed at 245 MPa (35 ksi), pre-reacted under a vacuum of 10^{-5} torr at 800 °C for 45 minutes, and then consolidated by hot isostatically pressing at 1350 °C and 175MPa (25 ksi) for two hours.

Isothermal and cyclic oxidation experiments were conducted over the temperature range of 950 °C to 1070 °C in air. Oxidation samples with a nominal thickness of 0.18 cm and a diameter of 0.6 cm were electro-discharge machined and polished to 0.3 μm alumina. Cyclic oxidation experiments to evaluate oxide adherence consisted of ten hour cycles at temperature followed by cooling in static air. Weight change measurements were used to determine the parabolic oxidation rate constant of the composites as described in several texts^{5,6}. Since alumina fibers exhibit negligible mass gain during elevated temperature exposure, weight gain calculations were based on the exposed surface area of the matrix. Oxide morphology, composition, and adherence were evaluated by x-ray diffraction, scanning electron microscopy (SEM), energy dispersive spectroscopy (EDS), and electron microprobe analysis (EMPA).

3. RESULTS

The composition of the matrix of the composites was determined using an electron microprobe and the results are presented in Table 1. As a result of diffusion between the TiAl matrix and the alumina-zirconia fibers during fabrication, the matrix of the composites reinforced with PRD166 fibers contains a small amount of zirconium. Ni₃Al and Ti₃Al composites reinforced with PRD166 composites have also been reported to be doped with zirconium after fabrication by pressure infiltration⁷. Zirconium was not detected in any of the composites containing FP fibers. X-ray diffraction confirmed that the matrices of the composites was gamma TiAl.

Table 1. Composition of As-Fabricated Composites

<u>Reinforcement</u>	<u>Titanium</u>	<u>Aluminum</u>	<u>Zirconium</u>
Monolithic	61.4 wt. %	38.8 wt. %	----
5% PRD166	61.3 wt. %	38.6 wt. %	0.06 wt. %
15% PRD166	59.6 wt. %	39.0 wt. %	0.12 wt. %
30% PRD166	61.1 wt. %	39.0 wt. %	0.17 wt. %
15% FP	62.9 wt. %	37.0 wt. %	----

3.1. TiAl & TiAl-FP Composites

The isothermal oxidation rate constants of monolithic TiAl and FP reinforced composites were calculated from mass change measurements at 950 °C, 1020 °C, and 1070 °C, and the results are presented in Figure 1. The oxidation rate of TiAl reinforced with pure alumina FP fibers is comparable to that of monolithic TiAl at 950 °C and 1020 °C. At 1070 °C, alumina reinforced composites exhibit greater oxidation resistance than the unreinforced matrix.

A model of the oxidation of TiAl containing 40 wt.% alumina has been presented elsewhere⁸. The thermodynamic stability of titanium oxide and aluminum oxide are similar, and, as a result, Ti-Al alloys form mixed oxides of TiO₂ and Al₂O₃. Increasing aluminum concentrations promote Al₂O₃ formation and shift the oxidation rate constant towards alumina formation, as illustrated by comparing the oxidation rate constants of TiAl and Ti₃Al in Figure 1.

SEM photomicrographs of the oxide scale formed on monolithic TiAl and on the FP reinforced composites are shown in Figure 2. At all temperatures, unreinforced TiAl formed a duplex oxide consisting of alternating layers of rutile and alumina. Meier⁹ has shown that at least 45 wt.% aluminum is necessary to form a continuous Al₂O₃ scale during oxidation in air at 1100 °C. Formation of the discontinuous alumina film depletes the substrate of aluminum and produces an environmentally induced phase transformation of TiAl to Ti₃Al, as shown in Figure 2. A similar phase transformation has been observed in Ni₃Al¹⁰, NbAl₃^{11,12}, and TiAl₃¹³. The lower aluminum content of the Ti₃Al zone promotes internal oxidation, producing Al₂O₃ precipitates (shown in Figure 2) which further reduce the local aluminum content.

The phases present after 100 hours of oxidation at 950 °C and 1070 °C were identified by x-ray diffraction and are tabulated in Table 2. In order to obtain information about the relative amount of oxides present, the ratio of the integrated x-ray intensity for alumina and rutile ($\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{TiO}_2$) were calculated from x-ray diffraction data and are presented in Table 2; calculations are based on the (116) and the (110) planes for alumina and rutile, respectively.

Based on x-ray diffraction data and SEM observations, rutile formation was more prevalent at 950 °C than at 1070 °C. Other researchers have made similar observations: Meier et al.⁹ noted that TiAl containing 45 wt.% aluminum formed a continuous alumina scale during oxidation at 1100°C but formed a thick rutile scale during oxidation at 800°C. Furthermore, Al_2O_3 fibers appear to promote Al_2O_3 formation, particularly at higher temperatures.

Table 2. Phases Present after Isothermal Oxidation (100 hours)

Reinforcement	Temp. (°C)	Major Phase	Minor Phase	$\frac{I_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}}{I_{\text{TiO}_2}}$
Monolithic	950	TiAl, Al_2O_3 , TiO_2 , Ti_3Al	---	0.56
Monolithic	1070	Ti_3Al , TiO_2 , Al_2O_3	TiAl	1.36
FP	950	TiAl, Al_2O_3	TiO_2	0.79
FP	1070	Al_2O_3 , TiAl	Ti_3Al , TiO_2	4.88

Alumina fibers do not affect the thermodynamics of alumina formation: that is, inert dispersoids do not alter the activity of aluminum or titanium in the matrix. Therefore, alumina fibers promote a continuous alumina scale on TiAl by altering the kinetics of oxide formation. At least two mechanisms may be proposed to explain the influence of alumina fibers on Al_2O_3 formation: 1) fibers act as nuclei or 2) fibers inhibit internal oxidation.

Aluminum fibers which intersect the surface of the composite may act as nucleation sites and, thereby, promote the formation of a continuous alumina scale. Oxide dispersoids (e.g., Y_2O_3 , CeO_2 , and ThO_2) have been shown to facilitate the formation of continuous Cr_2O_3 scales on nickel-chromium alloys^{14,15}. Using a transmission electron microscope to observe oxidation in-situ, Wilcox¹⁶ experimentally confirmed that nucleation does occur on oxide particles.

Another possibility is that Al_2O_3 fibers may act as internal oxides and promote a transition from internal oxidation to external oxidation. As illustrated in Figure 2, TiAl containing 40 wt.% aluminum forms internal oxides of Al_2O_3 , particularly in the aluminum depleted Ti_3Al zone. The formation of the internal oxide precipitates consumes the supply of aluminum in the substrate and, consequently, is detrimental to the establishment of an exclusive alumina scale.

Wagner¹⁷ derived an expression for the critical aluminum content, N_{Al}^* , necessary to prevent internal oxidation. The critical aluminum content is dependent on the volume fraction of internal precipitates, g , and the ratio of the diffusivity of oxygen and aluminum in the matrix, $D_{\text{O}}/D_{\text{Al}}$. Other variables in Equation 1 include the oxygen solubility in the alloy, N_{O}^s , and the molar volumes of the oxide, V_{ox} , and of the alloy, V_{m} . According to Wagner, internal oxide precipitates block the ingress of oxygen into the alloy. At a critical volume fraction of internal precipitates, g^* , the oxygen flux is reduced sufficiently to allow the formation of a continuous alumina film.

$$N_{\text{Al}}^* \geq \left[\frac{\pi g^* N_{\text{O}}^s D_{\text{O}} V_{\text{m}}}{3 D_{\text{B}} V_{\text{ox}}} \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (1)$$

If the alumina reinforcements act as internal precipitates, then it may be possible to form a continuous Al_2O_3 film at a lower aluminum content than without the reinforcements.

3.2. TiAl-PRD166 Composites

The specific weight gains resulting from isothermal oxidation at 950 °C of TiAl composites reinforced with 5, 15, and 30 vol.% PRD166 fibers are shown in Figure 4; similar trends were observed during oxidation at 1020 °C and 1070 °C. For composites containing 15 and 30 vol.% fibers, reinforcing with PRD166 fibers is detrimental to the isothermal oxidation resistance: the specific weight gain increases proportionally with the volume fraction of PRD166 fibers. TiAl-5% PRD166 composites and monolithic TiAl exhibited similar oxidation kinetics.

During oxidation at 950 °C, 1020 °C, and 1070 °C, TiAl-PRD166 composites formed a multiphase scale composed of rutile, alumina, and zirconia. Examination of oxide cross sections indicated that rutile formation was more prevalent at 950 °C than at 1070 °C. As shown in Figure 5, a dark phase, which was identified as Al_2O_3 by EMPA and EDS, formed along the perimeter of the PRD166 fibers.

Oxygen diffusion through PRD166 fibers and subsequent oxidation of the matrix is responsible for Al_2O_3 formation along the perimeter of PRD166 fibers and the accelerated oxidation rate of the TiAl-PRD166 composites. Oxygen diffusion along PRD166 fibers has recently been reported in Ni_3Al -PRD166 composites^{7,18}. The grain size of polycrystalline PRD166 fibers is extremely fine: 0.5 μm and 0.2 μm for alumina and zirconia grains, respectively. The fine grain size may promote rapid grain boundary diffusion through the fibers. In addition, the diffusivity of oxygen in zirconia at 1070 °C is more than eleven orders of magnitude greater than in Al_2O_3 ^{19,20}. At this rate, oxygen diffusing through zirconia in the ~ 1 mm long PRD166 fibers could reach the center of the oxidation samples (~0.15 cm thick) in less than 1.6 hours at 1070 °C.

A reaction was observed adjacent to some of the PRD166 fibers, particularly at fiber clusters, after oxidation in air at 950 °C, 1020 °C or 1070 °C. EMPA revealed that the dark precipitates shown in Figure 4 are Al_2O_3 and that the matrix was doped with approximately 2.5 wt.% zirconium. The extent of internal oxidation grew proportional to the square root of time.

The matrix-PRD166 reaction does not result from an inherent fiber-matrix chemical incompatibility. Diffusion couple experiments have shown that Al_2O_3 is stable with gamma TiAl^{21} . Above 1000 °C, zirconia is thermodynamically more stable than alumina.

The reaction observed around some of the PRD166 fibers results from internal oxidation. Oxygen diffuses along or through surface connected PRD166 fibers and radially into the TiAl matrix. The critical aluminum content necessary to prevent internal oxidation, as shown by Equation 1, is dependent on the ratio of oxygen and aluminum diffusivity in the matrix, $D_{\text{O}}/D_{\text{Al}}$. It is believed that zirconium, which is present in the matrix adjacent to the PRD166 fibers, increases the oxygen diffusivity in the matrix and, consequently, promotes internal oxidation along the perimeter of the fibers. Zirconium has been shown to increase the oxygen diffusivity in titanium²².

3.3. Oxide Adherence

From an oxidation point of view, perhaps the most technologically important aspect of composites is the potential effect of inert fibers or dispersoids on oxide adherence. As illustrated by Figure 5, as a result of their excellent oxide adherence, the cyclic oxidation resistance of TiAl-PRD166 and TiAl-FP composites is vastly superior to that of monolithic TiAl. In contrast to the composites, monolithic TiAl exhibited extensive cracking and spalling of the external oxide scale during cyclic oxidation.

SEM observations of oxide scales on TiAl show that the thickness of the outer TiO_2 layer increases with time, thus indicating that TiO_2 grows by outward cation diffusion which may produce voids at the oxide-metal interface. Voids are observed at the oxide-metal interface during the oxidation of TiAl alloys, and oxide spallation is often observed at this interface.

Alumina fibers may improve the oxide adherence on TiAl alloys by promoting Al_2O_3 formation and, thereby, inhibiting TiO_2 formation and void formation at the scale-matrix interface. Perkins²³ showed that a continuous alumina layer, promoted by chromium and vanadium additions, prevented the formation of an external TiO_2 scale and improved the oxide adherence of the alloy. Other studies²⁴ have demonstrated improved cyclic oxidation resistance of Ti-Al alloys with alumina or TiAl_3 coatings.

Alumina fibers also may form a bond with the external oxide and anchor the scale to the TiAl substrate. Direct evidence of fiber pegging is shown in Figure 6; the oxide bows away from the metal substrate but is securely anchored at fiber reinforcements. The improved oxide adherence

on the TiAl composites most likely results from both kinetic and mechanical pegging effects of the inert alumina fibers.

4. SUMMARY

TiAl reinforced with PRD166 fibers exhibited increased weight gain during oxidation in air, as compared to monolithic TiAl and TiAl reinforced with pure alumina fibers. Oxygen diffusion through the PRD166 fibers and oxidation of the matrix along the alumina reinforcement are responsible for the accelerated oxidation rate. Zirconium from the PRD166 fibers increased the oxygen diffusivity in the TiAl matrix and promoted internal oxidation adjacent to the fibers.

The addition of FP or PRD166 fibers significantly improved the oxide adherence during cyclic oxidation. Direct evidence of fiber pegging was observed.

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Figure 1. Parabolic oxidation rate constant of TiAl and TiAl-Al₂O₃ composites compared to the rate constant of TiO₂ and Al₂O₃ formation. (Data from references 25, 26 and 27)

Figure 2. Oxide scale after 100 hours of isothermal oxidation at 1070 °C: (a) monolithic TiAl and (b) TiAl-15% FP. "A" denotes external TiO₂ scale, "B" denotes Al₂O₃ layer, "C" indicates a mixed TiO₂ and Al₂O₃ zone, "D" shows internal oxides in the Ti₃Al zone "E" and arrow denotes porosity at the oxide-Ti₃Al interface.

Figure 3. Specific weight gain of TiAl and TiAl-PRD166 composites during isothermal oxidation at 950°C.

Figure 4. (a) External oxide scale and (b) PRD166-matrix reaction in TiAl 30% PRD166 after 100 hours at 1070 °C. "A" denotes external alumina scale, "B" denotes localized formation of TiO₂ and "C" shows ZrO₂ in the oxide scale.

Figure 5. Specific weight change during cyclic oxidation at 1070°C. One cycle corresponds to 10 hours of isothermal oxidation followed by air cooling to room temperature.

(a)

(b)

Figure 6. External oxide scale on TiAl-15% PRD166 composite after 100 hours of cyclic oxidation at 950 °C. (a) low magnification (b) higher magnification